

Article

Agricultural technology & Agrarian Social Change in Western Uttar Pradesh

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Abstract

The objective of this paper is to discuss the impact on agricultural technology on the social structure of agrarian Uttar Pradesh

Key terms

Agrarian social formation, New farm technology, social equity, relative deprivation

Introduction

Introduction of new-farm technology (Irrigation, Fertilizers, and HYVs) in the latter half of 1960s has brought about enormous changes in the traditional agricultural system, in north-western

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region of India particularly in Punjab, Haryana, and western Uttar Pradesh. It has been largely because of large scale irrigation facilities available in these regions. Village studies on Uttar Pradesh show that the new farm technology has led to important consequences in agrarian social formation of the most populous state. On the one hand, it has led to an increase in agricultural productivity and on the other it has increased the inequality between the rich and poor. This process seriously poses the question of social equity and raises the level of relative deprivation. This has led to a drastic change in the agrarian relationship and changed the socio-economic profile of agrarian society of Uttar Pradesh. In the last few decades there is greater use of new farm technology, and this has led to a change in the cropping pattern and crop intensity. Due to all this the agrarian social formation has undergone a sea-change in the state. New farm technology is one of the most important factors to bring about change in the overall agrarian social formation. This therefore necessitates an in-depth study on this issue to analyze and understand emerging agrarian social formation and its relations with new farm technology. The objective of this paper is to find out further changes in agrarian social formation in Uttar Pradesh due to the introduction of new farm technology. The paper also tries to explore the changes brought about by the introduction of new farm technology with respect to female education, employment opportunities, migration and Jajmani system.

India is predominantly an agrarian economy. More than two-third of its population depends on primary sector. Large majority consist of small farmers. Many changes have been observed in agrarian structure especially in agrarian relations in pre and post independent India. The British introduced three different

types of revenue settlement patterns (Zamindari, Rayatwari, and Mahalwari) in the country, which brought about changes in Indian agrarian structure. After independence land reform acts, land ceiling, abolition of Zamindari system, and different development programmes also brought the substantial changes in the agrarian relations. The introduction of high yielding varieties of seeds after 1965 and increased use of fertilizers, irrigation and mechanization of agriculture are known collectively as the green revolution, which provide the increase in production needed to make India self sufficient in food grains thus improving agriculture in India (Wikipedia, the free encyclopedia). Introduction of new farm technology, HYVs, irrigation and fertilizers increased the production and productivity in different parts of the country such as Punjab, Haryana, and western Uttar Pradesh etc.

Administratively U.P. can be divided into four regions: (i) Western region, (ii) Central region, (iii) Eastern region, and (iv) Bundelkhand region. The share of agriculture in the total reporting area ranges from less than 70 per cent in the Central, Eastern and Bundelkhand regions to 75 per cent in the Western region. Area under forest is ranging from around 5 per cent in Western to 9 per cent in the Eastern region. Western region is characterized as the food and sugar basket of Uttar Pradesh. Rice and wheat are the main food grains crops. The Western region is far ahead in adoption of improved technology as compared to other regions in Uttar Pradesh (U.P. Development Report, 2007: 28-33). Since the beginning of the 20th century in Western U.P., the historical factors were acting positively towards expansion of cultivation of commercial crops: the prevalence of 'Khudkasht' proprietors (cultivator-owners), public investment in irrigation, availability of credits and sugar mills (Neale, 1962). While in

Eastern UP parasitic 'Zamindars' (landlords), absence of public investment in irrigation, rigid revenue burdens had reduced the mass of the peasantry to such a pauperized situation, who are dependent on merchants and moneylenders, that the loss of genuinely independent small producers and middle peasants had been reduced to insignificance (Thorner, 1976).

Western U.P. was historically the most dynamic region in India, with the highest rate of growth of both foodgrains and commercial crops output. Under a moderate Khudkast system (Bhaichara system), it enjoyed the benefits of the heaviest concentration of public investment in canal irrigation along with Punjab in whole India. After Independence, the region emerged as one of the least polarized class structures and with strong and large class of independent producers. Thus, conditions were exceptionally favourable in this region for widespread adoption of cultivation of cash crops. This is not to say that it was benefiting all rural households (Siddique, 1999).

Farm mechanization led to increase in input due to higher average cropping intensity, larger area, and increased the productivity of farm labour. Furthermore, farm mechanization increased agricultural productivity and profitability on account of timeliness of operation and better quality of work and more efficient utilization of crop inputs. Mechanization also led to increase in human labour employment for the on-farm and off-farm activities as a result of manufacture, repair, servicing and sail of tractors and improved farm equipment (Verma, 2008). The jajmani relationship has now been supplanted in many villages; although in relatively few has it completely disappeared. It has been supplanted mainly because more money is now used in

village economy and modern transport makes market transactions more feasibly. Cash crops are usually not included in jajmani arrangements. A worker or artisan who is paid with a load of sugarcane can only try to sell it, and he prefers to get the money in first place. Where food grains are raised for sale, money may prefer to pay for their shaves and pots with cash at market centers and towns and do their work there (Orentlein, 1962, pp. 313, 316; Karve and Damle, 1963, p. 37).

Yet the advantages of jajmani for economic stability and security are still sufficiently great that many villagers want to continue with at least some such arrangements. At times of peak demand for labour, a farmer is more likely to get help from jajmani associates than from those who can charge whatever the market will bear. The workers, in their turn, get more assured employment and a verity of gifts and concessions, which together may amount to more than money wages could buy in the villages. In recent decades, when grain has regularly been scarce and the value of the rupee whimsical, payment in grain is often preferred (Mandelbaum, 2005). In spite of continuous impact of modern agricultural practices, the rural social institutions remain visible; but not in same traditional form. Higher level of technological complexity has replaced the traditional family labour and exchange labour in different labour agricultural operations with specialized contractual labour. In case of jajmani relation, the mundane basis of traditional jajmani surely has undergone changes, but its ritual ideology, the spirit of reciprocity still looms in the mind of rural people. The payment are not more in kind, there may not be the annual bartan relationships, caste councils may not be any more mediating these relationships, but the monopoly of service castes over their

service specialists still hold in the villages (Mishra, 2008: 431).

Adoption of technological innovations on the one hand saved much of manual labour and on the other increased the productivity (Doshi and Jain, 1999: 350-51). But all section is not benefited equally. Only a section of agrarian society derived maximum advantage and the bulk of the population suffered. It created a wide gape between the peasants and agricultural labourers (Mathur, 1987: 12). It also increased income disparities. C. Bowles had observed as early as 1967 that, "the dramatic increase in food output which are occurring and should continue to grow in the years ahead, may lead to sharp disparities in income, which in turn may create an expanding sense of economic and social injustice" (Bowles, 1969: 83). The new capital-intensive agricultural strategy of mid sixties not only displaced a large number of agricultural labourers and small peasants, as they were becoming redundant, but also forced the small farmers to sell their land to rich one. A new breed of farmers, e.g. doctors, lawyers, businessmen, retired military and civil servants, constitute a new type of "gentlemen farmers" (Beteille, 1974: 86) emerged, who often successfully use their wide range of knowledge, experience and social contacts to develop a viable organization on their farm and transformation of black money into white money (Beteille, 1976: 93).

The agrarian revolution transformed a system of production for subsistence into the production of cash crops for the market, the surplus being made possible by reformed and mechanized cultivation (Oxford, A Dictionary of Sociology, 2004: 53). Green revolution brought a wide-ranging readjustment in the social institution. Obviously, a rigid caste hierarchy, a Jajmani arrangement and other similar

institutions, which were suited to the peasant system, no longer, fit into the changed society that is emerging (Aggarwal, 1978: 256). Mechanization in agriculture has brought changes in family members and women participation in agricultural work. Mechanization has also strengthened the familistic and reciprocal exchange mode of work (Satyanarayana, 1985: 03). Female labour consistently contributed more than male labour across the farm in all the operations except land preparation and sowing (Arya and Sarhadi, 2002: 582).

The adoption of new technology and seeds has made possible the cultivation of two or more crops on rotation on the same land in a year. It implies growth in volume of agricultural work and constraint of time since harvesting and thrashing of the previous crop must be completed quickly to leave time for the preparation for land for following crops (Byres, 1981: 412; Dasgupta, 1977: 101). In turn it has resulted in the more seasonal peaks of labour demand. The new technology and high yielding varieties of seeds have led to the proletarianization of small land owners and to be concentrated of land in fewer hands (Oommen, 1975: 151-167; Dasgupta, 1977: 256-260). A greater technical division of labour has been identified in the context of tractors and fertilizers (Desai, 1969: 25). Proletarianization of peasants is a main consequence of mechanization in agriculture. The proletarianization of the peasants implies a transformation in the mode of work from familistic and mutual exchange pattern of work to extra familistic type (Satyanarayana, 1985: 04). Modernization of agriculture has led not only to an increase in productivity and integration of agriculture in the broader national market, but also brought about the fundamental change in the social relations of production leading to the patronage and institutional

dependency relationships (Sabharwal, 2001: 179). Mechanization has been increasing among the farmers. Meanwhile, many traditional agricultural crops/species has shown a severe decline in the trend indicating a clear shift in cropping pattern. Majority of farmers depend upon migratory labourers now. Farmers purchase machinery not only to meet their agricultural requirement but also as a prestige issue. The *jajmani* system is not preventing in villages any longer (Singh, 2008).

During the green revolution, pesticides and other chemical residues in our food and overall reduced quality of food have led to a marked increase in various diseases, mainly various forms of cancer and reduced body immunity. Fertilizers have a short-term effect on productivity but a longer-term negative effect on the environment where they remain for years after leaching and running off, contaminating ground water and water bodies (Singh and Kumar, 2007: 5). According to a research report published in national daily, due to the imbalance use of chemical fertilizers the soil fertility is decreasing in U.P. since last decades. State government has confessed that it is difficult to achieve 5.1 per cent agricultural growth rate with decreasing soil fertility (Hindustan Daily newspaper, 23 April, 2008).

Methodology

This paper is based on pilot survey conducted in two villages of Meerut district of Uttar Pradesh. A sample of twenty farmers and ten landless labourers selected from each village. Thus, in all sixty respondents were selected for the present study. The data are collected with the help of structured interview schedule and participant observation. For the secondary data census,

statistical records and published materials etc. studied thoroughly.

main source of drinking water is private hand pumps. There is no arrangement for tap water supply.

Area of Study

For the present study two villages 'Khatki' and 'Saidipur Sadipur urf Ramnagar' of Parichhatgarh block in Meerut district is selected purposely.

Villages Profile: Khatki

The village Khatki is situated in Parichhatgarh block of Meerut district approximately 24 km. from the district headquarters in North. The total population of the village is 2439. SC population is 9.1% of the total population. The sex ratio is 876. Village has 503 households and the size of household is 6.8. The average literacy rate is 70.1%. There are several castes in the village like Gosai, Jat, Bhramans, Saini, Lohar, Bhadai, Nai, Chamar, Bhangji, etc. Gosai caste is numerically, politically and economically dominant in the village. The village head men also belong to Gosai caste. There is two primary schools in the village. Many children go to Parichhatgarh for education. Roads are good. Village is electrified. Most of the villagers are engaged in agricultural work. The main means of transportation are private buses, tempo and tongas, which are frequently available between the village, block and Meerut. The river Ganga is approximately 12 km. in north from the village. A small river is also lies near the village, which was the main source of irrigation. But at present there is huge shortage of water since 5-6 years. So, farmers arrange their own private tub wells and pumping sets for irrigation. Sugarcane and wheat are the main crops of the village. The

Ramnagar

The village Ramnagar is situated in Parichhatgarh block of Meerut district approximately 24 km. from the district headquarters in North. The total population of the village is 2300, which consist of 1263 male and 1037 female. SC population is 195, which is 8.51% of the total population. The sex ratio is 821. Village has 335 households and the size of household is 6.9. Literacy rate of male and female is 77.0% and 37.5% respectively. The average literacy rate is 59.1%. There is several castes in the village like Gujjars, Bhramans, Lohar, Bhadai, Nai, Dhiwer, Chamar, Bhangji, etc. Some Muslim households are also in the village. Gujjar are numerically, politically and economically dominant in the village. The village head man also belongs to Gujjar caste. There are two primary schools in the village. Many children go to Parichhatgarh for education. Roads are good. Village is electrified. But approximately 50% of the households have legally connection. The main means of transportation are private buses, tempo and Tongas, which are frequently available between the village, block and Meerut. Village is one km. inside from the main roads. There is no regular means of transportation. Most of the villagers are engaged in agricultural work and animal husbandry. The river Ganga is approximately 14 km. in north from the village. A small river is also lies near the village, which was the main source of irrigation. But at present there is huge shortage of water since 5-6 years. So, farmers arrange their own private tub wells and pumping sets for irrigation. Sugarcane and wheat are the main crops of the village. Some

villagers are in Government and private jobs outside the village. The main source of drinking water is private hand pumps.

Analysis of Data

1. General Information

The data collected from 40 households show that all the respondents are Hindu. Out of them 33 respondents (82.5%) belong to OBC and rest of the 17 respondents (17.5%) belong to General category. Large majority of the households (30) belong to joint family and rest of households (10) belong to nuclear family. All the respondents have their own, pucca and electrified house. The main source of drinking water is private hand pumps. Majority of the households use traditional method (fire wood and cow-dung cake) with partial use of LPG. Only two households use LPG for cooking. All the households have their own television for entertainment. Large majority of the households (32) have two wheelers and only eight households have four wheeler. Large majority of the households (34) have either land line phone or mobile phone or both. Large majority of households (42.5%) are middle farmers, the size of their land holding is 4-10 hec.

Analysis of data shows that most of the households have all the basic materialistic goods. We may conclude that villagers have great impact of technology and they are influenced by urban life pattern.

2. Changing Relations of Malik and Mazdoor

During the last decades drastic changes have taken place in relations between Malik and Mazdoor. In the traditional agricultural system, most of the agricultural work done by family members with the help of permanent and casual labourers. Increasing use of agricultural technology like High Yielding Varieties, irrigation and chemical fertilizers has changed traditional relation of Malik and Mazdoor. Adoption of agricultural technology has increased the crops intensity. Farmers are taking 2-3 crops in a year. The demand of labourers is very high during peak seasons like crop transplanting and harvesting. Except the peak season labourers remained unemployed during rest of the peak season. Farmers do not want to pay whole the years for the permanent labourers. So, they hired daily wages labourers according to their needs. Due to both the situations local labourers and migrant labourers are suffered enormously. So labourers organized groups and provide services on contract basis, which develop contractual relationships between Malik and Mazdoor. It is found in the survey that only two or three persons of a family are engaged in agricultural works. Therefore, they have to depend on agricultural labourers. Data shows that only 12 households have permanent labourers and 23 households prefer contract labourers for their agricultural work. For the harvesting of sugarcane, wheat and paddy they preferred contractual labourers.

3. Changing Jajmani System

Jajmani as an inter-jati exchange relation, though not unique, is one of the important features of traditional rural life in India. Under the relationship the patron, who is entitled to receive specialized services, is called jajmans and the person rendering these services are called kamin. In both the villages there are few numbers of households who bear jajmani

relations. Most of the service castes either left their traditional occupation or working in or near by town or cities for cash payment. In the study it is found that only Nai is working in considerable number of households under jajmani system.

After independence Jajmani system is disappearing from the village society. Implementation of agricultural technology since late 1960s is one of the most important factor which is responsible for declining jajmani system. 92.5% of respondents show that in the last two decades Jajmani system is declined.

In the village most of the farmers are depend on agricultural technology like HYVs, irrigation, chemical fertilizers, tractors and agricultural machinery etc. Agricultural machinery have reduced the work of lohar and bhadi with great extent. Most of the agricultural instrument used for manual work at fields have no more use in the recent period. Size of land holding is also one of the most important factors which affect all socio-economic aspects of agrarian society. The pattern of jajmani system significantly varies with land holding pattern of farmers. Marginal and small farmers in large number do not hold the jajmani system while among large farmers jajmani system exists.

Traditional joint family system is one of the most important features of the agrarian society. At present traditional joint family system is breaking down due to different reasons. Data show that 60% of joint families maintain jajmani system, whereas only 20% of nuclear families maintain jajmani system. We may conclude that declining traditional family system is significantly correlated with declining jajmani system.

4. Migration

Introduction of agricultural technology brought drastic changes in employment opportunities, wages and working conditions. In traditional agriculture system most of the family members were engaged in agriculture. It is found in the studies only one or two family members manage the agricultural work with the help of agricultural technology. Technology provides the ground to the family members to migrate outside the village for different reasons like services, business and education etc.

It is found that 71.43% of households with technology show out migration, whereas only 33.33% of households without technology show out migration. Thus, we may conclude that new farm technology plays significant role in migration. The data show that 76.67% of households with joint family show out migration, whereas only 10% of households with nuclear family show out migration. Thus, joint family system provides greater chances of migration. Pattern of household's migration significantly varies with land holdings pattern of farmers. Migration from marginal and small farmers' household is less whereas middle and large farmers show greater migration. Thus, we may conclude that large landholding significantly has greater chances of migration.

5. Health

Health is one of the most concerned factors of rural life. Analysis of data shows that most of the farmers consult private doctors and hospitals at Parichhatgarh. But for the serious problem they have to go to Meerut. Most of the agricultural labourers go to primary/community health centers for treatment because of their economic condition.

6. Education

New farm technology has great impact on education system of rural society. Most of the family members were engaged in traditional agricultural system. Implementation of new farm technology reduced the chances of engagement of family members (mainly children) in agricultural works. It also strengthens the economic condition of rural society. So, we may conclude that adoption of new farm technology increases the opportunities of getting education. All the respondents are keen to provide education to their children. They preferred private institutions for education of their wards. But due to poor economic condition they have to send their children to governments' school. It is found that all the children above five years are enrolled in schools.

7. Employment, Wages and Working Condition etc

To know the impact of new farm technology on different aspects like Employment, Wages and Working Condition etc, 20 landless agricultural labourers are interviewed. Analysis of data shows that they hardly get 3-4 months employment from the agricultural work. Implementation of new farm technology is one of the most important factors which reduced the employment opportunities to the great extent. To meet their family expenses they have to depend on non agricultural work and animal husbandry. During the last decades working condition has improved. Mostly labourers get cash payment for their labour. Mostly male labourers like non-agricultural works. Nobody wants to be a permanent laborer. They think that your expected life may be 30, 45 and 60 years if you work in three different fields like agriculture, non-agricultural work and government sector.

Conclusion

The analysis of data arrives at the conclusion that agricultural technology has brought great changes in socio-economic life of rural people. Relationship of malik and mandoor has changed from traditional to contractual. The jajmani system is also crumbling down. New farm technology, traditional family system and large land holding are some important factors in maintaining the jajmani system at present. New farm technology also provides the ground to out migration in search of education, services and business etc. To meet the demand of agricultural labourers during the peak seasons in migration labourers from native state has increased. Most of the service castes has left their traditional occupation or shifted towards the town and cities for the better employment opportunities and cash payment.

Adoption and consequences of agricultural technology is not uniform through out the state. To find out the consequences of agricultural technology there is a need of intensive study.

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